

REVIEW

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Edible Food Packages: An Approach towards Sustainable Future

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Abstract

The excessive use of non-biodegradable synthetic plastics in food packaging has led to environmental pollution, waste accumulation, and challenges in waste management, driving the need for sustainable alternatives. Edible packaging composed of food-grade, biodegradable, and naturally derived materials, has emerged as a promising solution. These films and coatings, made from polysaccharides, proteins, lipids, or composite materials, can serve as primary packaging by acting as barriers to moisture, oxygen, gases, and microbes, while incorporating active agents like antimicrobials, antioxidants, and vitamins to enhance food safety, sensory qualities, and shelf life. Plasticizers, emulsifiers, plant extracts, and antioxidants are added to improve mechanical, structural, and functional properties. Applications of edible coatings have demonstrated effective preservation of fruits, vegetables, and perishable foods by reducing microbial growth, delaying ripening, and minimizing weight loss. Nanotechnology further enhances edible films by enabling nanoencapsulation of bioactive agents, improving solubility, stability, and controlled release, though careful regulation is required due to the potential toxicity of nanoparticles. The global edible packaging market is rapidly growing, reflecting rising consumer demand for eco-friendly and sustainable products. Despite its advantages, industrial-scale adoption is limited by mechanical, barrier, and cost challenges, highlighting the need for continued research to optimize material properties and enable commercial feasibility.

Keywords: Edible films; Biodegradable packaging; Sustainable food packaging; Nanotechnology; Food packaging

Introduction

The accumulation of non-biodegradable synthetic plastics is a major environmental issue, contributing to pollution, harmful emissions, and disruption of the carbon cycle due to their inability to decompose. With over 320 million tons of plastic produced annually more than 40% used for disposable packaging urban areas face growing waste management challenges. This highlights the urgent need for eco-friendly alternatives. In response, biodegradable and edible films and coatings have gained significant attention as sustainable substitutes for conventional plastic packaging. Food packaging is crucial in protecting food from damage and spoilage, maintaining hygiene and safety, and reducing food waste. Over 30% of food is lost to spoilage during transportation or harvesting, ending up in landfills. As a key part of the food supply chain, effective packaging helps minimize such waste, making it essential in food production and distribution (Aguirre-Joya et al., 2018).

Edible packaging serves best as primary packaging and should be combined with bio-based, biodegradable secondary packaging for hygiene. However, replacing conventional plastics is challenging due to their established systems. Since this transition is still in its infancy, sustainability assessments are vital to avoid long-term risks. A shift toward a circular, bio-based economy, supported by initiatives like the UN 2030 Agenda and European Green Deal, is essential for fostering sustainable businesses (Gerassimidou et al., 2021). Conventional packaging, typically discarded

after a single use, relies on materials like paper, plastic, glass, steel, and aluminium. Despite moderate recycling rates for paper (>20%), plastics are recycled far less (<20%), creating a major environmental burden. Plastics, derived mainly from petroleum (e.g., polyethylene, polypropylene, PET), remain popular due to their light weight and ease of molding, but their non-sustainable nature poses significant challenges (Ahmadi et al., 2020).

Edible packaging is a sustainable, biodegradable alternative that helps maintain food quality, extend shelf life, reduce waste, and improve cost efficiency. Edible films are especially promising due to their versatility, ability to be produced from various materials, and role as carriers of antioxidants or antimicrobials. This has driven growing research interest over the past decade, though challenges remain for safe and effective industrial-scale application (Restrepo et al., 2018).

Edible packaging

Edible packaging can be neutral, active, or intelligent. Active types release compounds like antioxidants, vitamins, or antimicrobials to extend shelf life, enhance safety, and improve sensory qualities. They are applied as thin films (<0.3 mm) or coatings that act as barriers to moisture, oxygen, and microbes while carrying protective agents. Made from safe, edible materials such as starches, cellulose, chitosan, gums, proteins, or lipids, their properties can be tailored by adjusting composition and thickness. Since fruits and vegetables respire, packaging should allow limited gas exchange and must be approved by food safety authorities. Edible packaging can be safe for consumption when proper safety measures are followed during processing, handling, and storage. An ideal edible film should possess good sensory qualities, microbial stability, mechanical strength, be toxin-free, safe for health, eco-friendly, and cost-effective. Like conventional packaging, it must undergo quality testing, with microbiological safety being a key factor (Jeevahan et al., 2018).

Scope of edible packaging

The global edible packaging market, valued at USD 680 million in 2022, is expected to grow from USD 710 million in 2023 to USD 1,050 million by 2030 at a CAGR of 5.6%. Made from biodegradable, plant-based, and natural materials safe for consumption, edible packaging eliminates the need for recycling or disposal while offering a sustainable alternative to conventional packaging. Rising consumer demand for eco-friendly products, along with increased investments from governments and manufacturers, is driving their adoption in the food and pharmaceutical sectors (Sharma et al., 2025).

Categories of edible packaging materials

Edible films and coatings must be both safe to eat and capable of forming a continuous layer. They are typically made from proteins, polysaccharides, lipids, or composites, with the choice depending on the food type and application method. Plasticizers are often added for flexibility, while additives like antimicrobials, colors, or flavors may be included to enhance functionality.

Polysaccharide-based packaging materials

Polysaccharides, the most abundant natural macromolecules, are widely used in edible packaging and can be sourced from microbes (xanthan gum, pullulan), animals (chitin, chitosan), plants (cellulose, starch, pectin), and marine sources (alginate). Their films are oil-free, tasteless, colorless, chemically stable, and adaptable for processing. They help prevent dehydration, surface darkening, and oxidative rancidity, thereby extending the shelf life of fruits, vegetables, shellfish, and meats. Polysaccharide coatings act as good oxygen and CO₂ barriers at low to moderate humidity, reducing respiration and gas exchange in fresh produce. However, due to their hydrophilic nature, they offer poor moisture resistance. Additionally, their high sorption capacity allows them to bind and remove toxic substances, such as metal ions and radionuclides, when consumed (Nesic et al., 2019).

- ***Cellulose films***

Cellulose is a renewable, biodegradable polysaccharide with good strength, stability, and film-forming ability but poor solubility limits its direct use. Derivatives such as methylcellulose, carboxymethylcellulose, hydroxypropyl methylcellulose, and cellulose acetate overcome this issue, offering strong oxygen, CO₂, and lipid barriers, though with weak water resistance, which can be improved by adding lipids (Acharya et al., 2017).

- ***Chitosan films***

Chitosan, a linear polysaccharide of N-acetyl-glucosamine and N-glucosamine, is obtained by alkaline deacetylation of chitin, the second most abundant polysaccharide after cellulose, found in crustacean shells, insects, and fungi. It is non-toxic, biodegradable, and biocompatible. While chitin

is insoluble in water and most solvents, conversion to chitosan makes it soluble in acidic media like dilute hydrochloric, formic, or acetic acid. Owing to its favorable physicochemical properties, chitosan is widely studied for food packaging applications (Mujtaba et al., 2019).

- **Starch films**

Starch, a low-cost, abundant, biodegradable polysaccharide, is widely studied for edible packaging. It consists of amylose, which provides film-forming ability, and amylopectin, whose branched chains create crystalline regions, while branching points form amorphous regions. Though starch granules are insoluble in cold water, heating disrupts their crystalline structure, allowing hydroxyl groups of amylose and amylopectin to interact with water and partially dissolve (Thakur et al., 2019).

- **Alginate films**

Alginate, a natural polysaccharide from brown seaweed, is composed of β -(1-4)-D-mannuronic (M-blocks) and α -L-guluronic acid (G-blocks). Its GM (β -(1-4)-D-mannuronic and α -L-guluronic acid block interactions give strong gelling properties. Alginate is non-toxic, biodegradable, biocompatible, biostable, and hydrophilic, making it suitable for edible packaging (Tong et al., 2023).

Protein-based packaging materials

Proteins, made of amino acids linked by peptide bonds, offer diverse mechanical and physical properties suitable for food coatings. Found as fibrous (insoluble) or globular (soluble) forms, they include gelatin, casein, whey, collagen, gluten, soy, bean, and peanut proteins. Protein-based coatings provide strong mechanical strength and effective barriers to gases, aromas, and lipids but have poor water resistance.

- **Milk protein films**

Casein-based films offer high transparency, firmness, elasticity, thermal stability, moderate hydrophobicity, and low oxygen permeability but, like most protein films, have poor water vapor resistance, which can be improved by combining with lipids. Tannic acid has been suggested as a crosslinking agent to enhance their properties. Caseinate, the common form of casein, is water-soluble but becomes insoluble at pH 4.6. Sodium and calcium caseinates are commercially produced by precipitating casein at pH 4.6, washing, neutralizing with NaOH or $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, and spray-drying. Whey proteins, available as whey protein isolates (WPI) and concentrates (WPC), are also widely used in edible films, with WPIs being the most common (Shendurse et al., 2018).

- **Collagen films**

Meat proteins include sarcoplasmic, stromal, and myofibrillar types, with stromal (collagen, elastin) and myofibrillar proteins used in edible films. Collagen, a fibrous stromal protein from connective tissues, skin, bones, and tendons by-products of meat processing is commonly applied as coatings for meat products. These films help reduce moisture loss, improve appearance, and enhance structural quality (Andonegi et al., 2020).

- **Gelatin films**

Gelatin, a water-soluble protein derived from collagen of fish, pork, or bovine sources, is tasteless, transparent, and slightly yellow. It is produced as Type A (acid-treated) or Type B (alkali-treated). Widely used in foods for gelling, texturizing, and emulsifying agent. Gelatin films offer good mechanical strength and low oxygen permeability but have poor thermal stability and high sensitivity to moisture and water vapour (Tyuftin and Kerry, 2021).

- **Zein films**

Zein, a corn prolamin protein soluble in 70–80% ethanol, shows thermoplastic, hydrophobic, antioxidant, and antibacterial properties. Its films are smooth, thermally stable, and effective barriers to O_2 , CO_2 , and oils but have poor mechanical strength and brittleness. Structural properties can be improved with plasticizers or polymer blends. Zein/chitosan films enriched with natural antimicrobials have shown potential for active packaging, reducing moisture loss, maintaining microbial quality, and extending fruit shelf life, making them a sustainable packaging option (Bayer, 2021).

Lipid-based packaging materials

Lipids, from plant, animal, or insect sources, are hydrophobic and mainly used in edible waxes, monoglycerides, or resins. They provide moisture-resistant coatings, often in composite films, as

they cannot form cohesive films alone. Natural waxes (carnauba, candelilla, rice bran, beeswax) or synthetic (paraffin, petroleum) offer strong hydrophobic barriers and are widely applied in edible packaging.

• Composite films

Composite films combine hydrophilic and hydrophobic compounds to enhance functional properties, compensating for the limitations of individual components. For example, adding lipids to polysaccharide or protein films improves water vapor resistance. The hydroxypropyl methylcellulose-chitosan coatings with bergamot essential oil effectively control grape respiration and weight loss, while gum acacia/pectin/pullulan blends with plasticizers extend the shelf life of ivy gourd (Luo et al., 2022).

Applications of edible packaging

Table 1. Application of edible packaging

Food product	Edible materials	Beneficial effect	Reference
Cherry tomato	Edible film incorporated with chitosan and liposome encapsulation of <i>Artemisia Annu</i> oil. Edible coating based on nanoemulsion-thymol-quinone protein/chitosan.	Inactivation of <i>Escherichia coli</i> O157:H7. Inhibition of <i>Botrytis cinerea</i> .	Robledo et al. (2018)
Tomato	Aloe vera-based edible coating	Delayed ripening and extended shelf life (up to 39 days compared to 19 days for the control sample).	Athmaselvi et al. (2013)
Cucumber	Corn starch and mint (<i>Mentha viridis L.</i>) extract edible coating.	Enhancement of shelf life and quality stored at room temperature/low temperature (25 °C/10 °C).	Raghav and Saini (2018)
Broccoli (fresh cut)	Chitosan coatings with bioactives: tea tree, rosemary, pollen and propolis, pomegranate and resveratrol.	Inhibitory effects on survival of <i>Escherichia coli</i> and <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	Alvarez et al. (2013)
Carrots	Protein, polyalcohol and polysaccharide coatings.	Shelf life prolongation	Villafañán et al. (2017)
Green beans	Antimicrobial coating formulation consisting of modified chitosan containing a nanoemulsion of mandarin essential oil.	Reduction of <i>L. Innocua</i> over the storage time, owing to synergistic antimicrobial effects and firmness.	Donsi et al. (2015)
Kiwifruit slices	<i>Opuntia ficus-indica</i> mucilage edible coating.	Significantly higher firmness and lower weight loss than untreated slices.	Allegra et al. (2017)
Apricot	Chitosan coatings.	Increased content of total phenolics and antioxidant activity	Varasteh et al. (2023)
Papaya (fresh cut)	Psyllium gum alone and in combination with sunflower oil.	Quality maintenance and shelf life improvement.	Yousuf and Srivastava (2015)
Apple	Nanochitosan-based coating.	Significantly reduced weight loss, respiration rate, ethylene production and peroxidase activity; slowed down softening process and improved the flesh color after the climacteric peak.	Gardesh et al. (2016)
Banana	A rice starch edible coating blended with sucrose esters.	Extended postharvest quality during ripening (at 20 ± 2 °C); effective in delaying ethylene biosynthesis and reducing respiration rate. Shelf life prolonged for 12 days.	Thakur et al. (2019)
Lime fruit	Pectin-based coating.	Progressive increase in shrivelling or wilting and loss in green colour during storage time; higher temperatures accelerated these changes.	Maftoonazad and Ramaswamy (2019)
Grape berry	Coatings based on carnauba wax-lemongrass oil nanoemulsions.	Antimicrobial effect by inhibition of <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> and <i>Escherichia coli</i> . Effective at reducing weight loss, firmness, phenolic compounds, and antioxidant activity.	Kim et al. (2014)

Additives in edible films

Additives enhance the structural, mechanical, and functional properties of edible films. Plasticizers like glycerol, sorbitol, sugars, and lipids increase flexibility and reduce brittleness by decreasing intermolecular interactions in polymer networks. Emulsifiers, including lecithins, monoglycerides, polysorbates, and some proteins, stabilize lipid dispersions and improve surface adhesion in composite films. Antimicrobials such as nisin, chitosan, plant extracts, essential oils, metal nanoparticles, and bacteriocins extend shelf life by inhibiting microbial growth. Plant extracts and essential oils (e.g., cinnamon, thyme, garlic, oregano) provide antioxidant and antimicrobial effects while enhancing mechanical and physicochemical properties. Antioxidants like tocopherols, BHT, BHA, ascorbic acid, polyphenols, and carotenoids delay oxidation; for instance, blackberry powder or β -carotene has been incorporated into starch-based films to improve antioxidant activity. Together, these additives enable edible films to serve as functional, protective, and bioactive packaging materials (Majeed et al., 2023).

Nanotechnology in edible films and coatings

Nanotechnology uses materials <100 nm, offering high reactivity and unique properties. Nanoscale edible coatings for foods like meat, fruits, and cheese provide water and gas barriers while incorporating antimicrobial and antioxidant agents to extend shelf life. Nanoadditives, such as chitosan nanoparticles or essential oil-loaded nanoclays, effectively inhibit microbial growth. However, small nanoparticles can penetrate human cells and pose toxicity risks, so their use must follow food safety regulations (Katiyar and Ghosh, 2021).

Conclusion

Edible packaging is emerging as a sustainable alternative to conventional petroleum-based materials, driven by consumer demand for eco-friendly, chemical-free foods. Made from food-grade, regulatory-approved materials, it incorporates biopolymers and natural active agents to extend shelf life by providing barriers to water, oxygen, aroma, and by adding antimicrobial and antioxidant properties. While not replacing conventional packaging, it serves effectively as primary packaging. Nanotechnology enhances edible films by improving solubility, stability, and controlled release of active agents through nanoencapsulation. Despite its potential, industrial-scale commercialization is limited by mechanical and barrier constraints and high costs, requiring further research to improve quality and reduce production expenses.

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Competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethics approval

Not applicable.

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